

Salicylaldehyde Complexes of Phenoxy Derivatives of Niobium(V) and Tantalum(V) Chlorides

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Compounds of composition $MCl_n(OC_6H_5)_{4-n}.Sal$, where $M=Nb$ or Ta ; $SalH=$ Salicylaldehyde and 'n' varies from 0-3 have been prepared and characterised by elemental analysis, conductance, magnetic susceptibility and infra-red spectral studies.

CCOORDINATION compounds of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) chloroalkoxides with ligands related to β -diketones are reported in the literature¹. A relatively stable series of acetylacetonate complexes which have been extensively investigated by various workers include $NbCl_2(OCH_3)_2.acac^{2,3}$, $NbBr_2(OCH_3)_2.acac^4$, $NbCl(OCH_3)_3.acac^4$ and $Nb(OCH_3)_4.acac^4$ and the corresponding tantalum complexes. Recently Kapoor et al⁵ followed by Schoenherr et al⁶ have isolated phenoxides of niobium and tantalum. We have recently reported some chelates of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) phenoxides with benzoin⁷. The present paper describes similar compounds of salicylaldehyde (SalH) with niobium(V) and tantalum(V) phenoxides.

Experimental

Phenoxy derivatives of niobium(V) and tantalum(V) viz. $MCl(OC_6H_5)_4$, $MCl_2(OC_6H_5)_3$, $MCl_3(OC_6H_5)_2$ and $MCl_4(OC_6H_5)$ were prepared by the published methods^{8,9}. Salicylaldehyde (Riedel) was used after distillation at reduced pressure. Compounds of composition $M(OC_6H_5)_4.Sal$, $MCl(OC_6H_5)_3.Sal$, $MCl_2(OC_6H_5)_2.Sal$ and $MCl_3(OC_6H_5).Sal$ were prepared by taking monochloro-, dichloro-, trichloro- and tetrachlorophenoxy derivatives of the metal as suspensions in benzene and adding salicylaldehyde in benzene dropwise in 1:1 molar ratio. The resulting solutions were refluxed for 5-6 hours when homogenous solution were obtained and yellow crystalline compound separated out on adding petroleum ether. These products were filtered off in a dry atmosphere, repeatedly washed with petroleum ether and dried under vacuum. Care was taken to avoid moisture.

The metals were estimated as their pentoxides and chlorine by Volhard's method. Magnetic susceptibility measurements were carried out at 298°K using Guoy's method. Conductance measurements were made with Toshniwal Conductivity Bridge Type CL01/01A using a cell of cell constant 0.384 at $25 \pm 0.1^\circ$. Infrared spectra were

scanned on a Perkin-Elmer Infrared Spectrophotometer model 330 and 621 using both nujol mulls and KBr pellets.

Results and Discussion

Stoichiometric composition of the compounds have been established by elemental analysis and are enlisted in Table 1. These include the series of compounds $MCl_n(OC_6H_5)_{4-n}.Sal$ ($M=Nb, Ta$), where 'n' varies from 0 to 3. All these are fine yellow crystalline compounds and are fairly soluble in benzene and nitrobenzene. Molar conductance values of millimolar solutions of the compounds in nitrobenzene (Table 1) suggest them to be non-

TABLE 1—ANALYTICAL DATA OF THE COMPOUNDS OF SALICYLALDEHYDE WITH NIOBIUM(V) AND TANTALUM(V) CHLORO-PHENOXIDES

Compound	Colour	Elemental Analysis				Molar conductance in nitrobenzene ($ohm^{-1}cm^2mole^{-1}$)
		Reqd. %		Found %		
		M	Cl	M	Cl	
$Nb(OC_6H_5)_4.Sal$	Yellow	15.87	—	15.31	—	3.56
$NbCl(OC_6H_5)_3.Sal$	Yellow	17.60	6.71	17.25	6.53	2.28
$NbCl_2(OC_6H_5)_2.Sal$	Yellow	19.75	15.07	19.30	14.92	1.97
$NbCl_3(OC_6H_5).Sal$	Yellow	22.50	25.76	22.11	25.20	1.92
$Ta(OC_6H_5)_4.Sal$	Lemon yellow	26.85	—	26.17	—	1.07
$TaCl(OC_6H_5)_3.Sal$	Lemon yellow	29.36	5.76	29.05	5.42	1.85
$TaCl_2(OC_6H_5)_2.Sal$	Lemon yellow	32.38	12.70	32.12	12.25	2.14
$TaCl_3(OC_6H_5).Sal$	Lemon yellow	36.10	21.23	35.60	20.93	2.33

electrolytes⁸. The compounds are diamagnetic which is in accordance with the earlier observation¹.

Pure salicylaldehyde has a carbonyl stretching frequency, $\nu(C=O)$ present at 1660 cm^{-1} ⁹ which is lowered by $60-80\text{ cm}^{-1}$ in their complexes. Besides this, $\nu(C-C)$ stretching mode which is present at

1200 cm⁻¹ in pure ligand is shifted to higher regions on complex formation. All the important bands which have been observed in the spectra of the compounds are given in Table 2. Reference to the

hence an octahedral structure may be proposed for these compounds. In case of tantalum compounds, the intense absorption bands around 330-340 cm⁻¹ are assigned to $\nu_{\text{Ta-Cl}}$, and are in the same range as reported earlier in literature for octahedral environment around the central atom¹⁸.

TABLE 2—MAJOR INFRARED SPECTRAL BANDS (cm⁻¹) OF SALICYLALDEHYDE AND THEIR COMPOUNDS

Compound	$\nu(\text{O-H})$	$\nu(\text{C=O})$	$\nu(\text{C-C})$	$\nu(\text{O} \rightarrow \text{M})$	$\nu(\text{M-Cl})$
Salicylaldehyde	3180s	1660s	1200s	—	—
Nb(OC ₆ H ₅) ₄ .Sal	—	1602vs	1230s	472s,br	—
NbCl(OC ₆ H ₅) ₃ .Sal	—	1595vs	1235vs	466s	242s
NbCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ .Sal	—	1580s	1225s	460s	350vs
NbCl ₃ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₁ .Sal	—	1590vs	1220vs	470s	352vs
Ta(OC ₆ H ₅) ₄ .Sal	—	1588vs	1232vs	570s	—
TaCl(OC ₆ H ₅) ₃ .Sal	—	1602vs	1230s	562s	335s, 304sh
TaCl ₂ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₂ .Sal	—	1590vs	1228s	578s	328s, 302sh
TaCl ₃ (OC ₆ H ₅) ₁ .Sal	—	1592vs	1225s	575s	325s, 308sh

vs=very strong; s=strong, sh=shoulder, br=broad.

spectra of other carbonyl compounds and their complexes with metal halides¹⁰⁻¹³ indicates that carbonyl oxygen of the ligand acts as the donor. The $\nu(\text{O-H})$ stretching frequency generally observed at 3180 cm⁻¹ in pure ligand¹⁴ is missing, which is also supported by the observation that hydrogen chloride gas is evolved during the course of reaction of chlorophenoxides with salicylaldehyde. This observation can be explained on the basis of following reaction:

Similarly the formation of other compounds can also be explained. No such band which could be assigned to the bridging M-O-M bonds except the one around 462-475 cm⁻¹ region in case of niobium compounds and in the region 560-580 cm⁻¹ in case of tantalum phenoxide adducts are observed. The bands in the above regions can be safely assigned to terminal $\nu(\text{M-O})$ stretching modes. These bands are in the same region as reported earlier in literature¹⁵. No band that could be assigned to M=O bond are present in the spectra of these compounds, thus excluding the possibility of abstraction of oxygen by these metals from the ligand¹⁶.

In the low frequency infrared spectra of these compounds sharp intense bands around 340-350 cm⁻¹ in case of niobium compounds have been observed. These bands are in close agreement with the reported $\nu_{\text{Nb-Cl}}$ vibrations for octahedral complexes¹⁷ and

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